

MECHANICAL ANALYSIS AND VISCOELASTIC MODELING OF A 3D INTERLOCK WOVEN COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this work is to study the cure and temperature dependent homogenized viscoelastic model of a composite material reinforced with three dimensional (3D) woven fabrics. First, the linearly viscoelastic behavior of a composite material made of 3D woven interlock fabrics and epoxy resin was experimentally studied. Rectangular composite plates were manufactured by Resin Transfer Molding (RTM). Three configurations were studied as follows to emphasize the future material response: warp tows oriented at 45° from the longitudinal plate direction, and weft and warp tows respectively oriented along the longitudinal plate direction. Creep tests were carried out with a universal testing machine using a tension fixture to study the viscoelastic behavior of the material at high temperatures. Six isothermals were tested from 120°C to 200°C, measuring the viscoelastic response below and above the glass transition temperature, T_g , of the resin. A mathematical modeling of the homogenized viscoelastic properties of the composite was developed in this work based on resin viscoelasticity and fabric geometrical homogenization. Finally, experimental results were compared to the cure and temperature dependent homogenized linear viscoelastic model developed in this work. This model is a step forward for the accurate prediction of the residual stresses development during the manufacturing of 3D woven interlock composites for structural parts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Studied during the last decades, 3D woven composites have finally reached the commercial aerospace industry in recent years. Some key components are now manufactured using composites reinforced with 3D interlock woven fabrics. 3D woven reinforcements where fibers are strategically placed through the thickness were developed over the last forty years to overcome the limitations of multiply laminates [1]. However, as it occurs in 2D laminates, uncontrolled deformations are often observed during the manufacturing of 3D woven composites. Processing related residual stresses, which induce part deformation, are mainly due to the resin cure shrinkage, the mismatch between the thermal expansion of the resin and fibers and the interaction between the tool and the part [2]. In the past, residual stresses have been numerically computed using elastic and viscoelastic models [3]. Thermoset resins show a viscoelastic behavior more pronounced at high temperatures, mainly above the glass transition temperature and low degrees of cure. For that reason, models as a function of degree of cure, temperature and time are required to obtain a more realistic prediction of the residual stresses development during the manufacturing of structural composite parts.

3D fabrics are manufactured from textile sewing techniques as stitching, braiding, knitting or weaving. Several architectures can be obtained with each technique. The general architectures of interlock woven fabrics were described by Ansar et al. [4]. Figure 1 is a geometrical representation of a typical through the thickness/angle interlock fabric where warp tows are intercalated through the thickness of the laminate to ensure a continuity of fibers in the inter-ply direction. Composites made of

3D interlock woven fabrics are generally manufactured by Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) (RTM or infusion processes).

Figure 1: 3D woven fabric: through the thickness/angle interlock woven architecture [5]

Based on the linearly viscoelastic constitutive theories formalized by Biot [6], with respect of the thermodynamics laws, nonlinearizing functions were introduced by Schapery [7] and recalled by Lévesque et al. [8]:

$$\begin{aligned} \boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) &= \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}(t) + \left(\frac{\partial p_3(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \otimes \mathbf{L}_2 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t) + p_3(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \mathbf{L}_2 \right) : \boldsymbol{\chi}(t) \\ p_1(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \mathbf{B} : \dot{\boldsymbol{\chi}} + p_2(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) \mathbf{L}_3 : \boldsymbol{\chi} + p_3(\mathbf{L}_2)^T : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{L} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{L}_1 & \mathbf{L}_2 \\ (\mathbf{L}_2)^T & \mathbf{L}_3 \end{bmatrix}$ and \mathbf{B} are symmetric and positive semi-definite, $\boldsymbol{\chi}$ are the internal variables and ϕ and $p_i(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon})$ are scalar functions of $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(t)$. The solution of the differential Equation (1) is

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma}(t) = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} + \left(\frac{\partial p_3}{\partial \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} \otimes \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + p_3 \mathbf{B} \right) : \int_0^t \Delta \mathbf{C}(\Phi - \Phi') : \frac{d}{d\tau} \left[\frac{p_3(\tau)}{p_2(\tau)} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}(\tau) \right] d\tau \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi - \Phi' = \int_r^t \frac{p_2(\gamma)}{p_1(\gamma)} d\gamma$ and $\Delta \mathbf{C}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{C}_k \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\omega_k}\right)$. ω_k are the relaxation times and \mathbf{C}_k

the relaxation tensors. The main challenge in modeling composites behavior is the fact that the resin state changes during processing depending on temperature and time. Cure (α) and temperature (T) dependencies have thus been studied in the literature to account for such changes [9 - 12].

Two implementation strategies have been developed to solve the viscoelastic constitutive theory in its integral form to prevent storing the whole loading history, for all the time steps, as recalled by Crochon et al. [13]. Equation (2) can be numerically solved by introducing a recursive expression between two time-steps [14] or finite-difference schemes (e.g., Euler, Crank-Nicholson) can be used to solve the first order differential equations from the integral differentiation [15].

Characterization of composite materials' viscoelastic behavior has been carried out by several authors in the past. For example, Ruiz and Trochu [9] performed relaxation tests on bidirectional glass/polyester composites using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA). Miyano et al. [16] carried out creep tests on unidirectional Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics (CFRP). Machado et al. [17] performed creep and relaxation tests at different loading angles on different woven reinforced thermoplastic matrix laminates.

The aim of this work was to characterize and predict the homogenized linear viscoelastic behavior of composite plates with 3D interlock woven fabrics. The paper is organized as follows: Section 2 describes the linearly viscoelastic model considering the degree of cure and temperature dependencies, Section 3 detailed the implementation strategy used to solve the constitutive equation in a finite element software. Then the experimental procedures carried out on composite plates are explained in Section 4.

2 CURE AND TEMPERATURE DEPENDENT LINEARLY VISCOELASTIC MODELING

The linearly viscoelastic model proposed by Courtois et al. [10] for an epoxy resin was written using the nonlinearizing functions introduced by Schapery [7], identifying $p_1 = a_T(T_g, \alpha)$ and $p_2 = p_3 = 1$:

$$\sigma(t) = \mathbf{C}_\infty : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \int_0^t \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{C}_k \exp \left[-\frac{1}{\omega_k} \left(\int_0^t \frac{1}{a_T(T_g, \alpha)} d\rho - \int_0^\tau \frac{1}{a_T(T_g, \alpha)} d\rho \right) \right] : \frac{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{d\tau} d\tau \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{C}_∞ is the fully relaxed tensor and $a_T(T, \alpha)$ are the shift factors used to construct master curves by applying the time-temperature superposition principle. The Arrhenius relationship [18, 16] was used to model the evolution of the shift factors as a function of temperature, below and above the glass transition temperature:

$$\begin{aligned} \log a_T(T, \alpha) &= -\frac{E_{a1}(\alpha)}{\ln(10)R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \text{ if } T < T_g \\ \log a_T(T, \alpha) &= -\frac{E_{a2}(\alpha)}{\ln(10)R} \left(\frac{1}{T} - \frac{1}{T_g} \right) \text{ if } T_g < T \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where E_{a1} is the activation energy (J/mol) and R is the universal gas constant. The reference temperature was set to the glass transition temperature, whose evolution as a function of degree of cure was modeled by the Di Benedetto relationship [19]:

$$\frac{T_g - T_{g0}}{T_{g\infty} - T_{g0}} = \frac{\lambda \alpha}{1 - (1 - \lambda) \alpha} \quad (5)$$

where λ is a material parameter, T_{g0} and $T_{g\infty}$ are the glass transition temperatures of the uncured and the fully cured resin, respectively. The cure-dependency of the parameters E_{a1} and E_{a2} were assumed linear. An analytical relationship was developed by Courtois et al. [10] to model the relaxation tensors evolution as a function of relaxation times, simulating a Gaussian curve with a plateau for the first relaxation times:

$$\begin{aligned} C_k(\omega) &= \left[\gamma \exp \left[-\left(\frac{\log \omega - \log \omega_{peak}}{l_{peak}} \right)^2 \right] + \beta \left[1 - \operatorname{erf} \left(\frac{\log \omega - \log \omega_{peak}}{l_{peak}} \right) \right] \right] \\ &\quad \times \frac{\log \omega_{k+1} - \log \omega_{k-1}}{2} (C_0 - C_\infty) \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $C_0 = C_\infty + \sum_{k=1}^N C_k$. γ , β , $\log \omega_{peak}$, l_{peak} are adjustable parameters related to the Gaussian peak height, the sigmoid plateau height, the position of the Gaussian peak on the relaxation times axis and the Gaussian peak width, respectively.

3 NUMERICAL IMPLEMENTATION

A recursive strategy was first used to implement the linearly viscoelastic model into the finite-element software Abaqus through a user material subroutine. Equation (3) was integrated and written in terms of internal variables, $\boldsymbol{\chi}$, and instantaneous relaxation tensor, \mathbf{C}_0 :

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}_0 : \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{C}_k \boldsymbol{\chi}_k \quad (7)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\chi}_k = \int_0^t \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t-\tau}{a_T \omega_k}\right) \right] \frac{d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}{d\tau} d\tau$.

The incremental form of Equation (7) yields to $\Delta\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C}_0 : \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \sum_{k=1}^N \mathbf{C}_k \Delta\boldsymbol{\chi}_k$ and $\Delta\boldsymbol{\chi}_k$ was developed as Machado et al. [17]:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\boldsymbol{\chi}_k &= \boldsymbol{\chi}_k^{n+1} - \boldsymbol{\chi}_k^n \\ &= \frac{\omega_k}{\Delta\xi} \left[\frac{\Delta\xi}{\omega_k} + \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta\xi}{\omega_k}\right) - 1 \right] \Delta\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} + \left[1 - \exp\left(\frac{-\Delta\xi}{\omega_k}\right) \right] (\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^n - \boldsymbol{\chi}_k^n) \quad \text{where } \Delta\xi = \frac{\Delta t}{a_T} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Finally, the complete homogenization of the composite material's viscoelastic properties was carried out numerically in Abaqus. The viscoelastic behavior of the matrix was defined by equations (3) to (8), while the geometry of the 3D interlock fabric was obtained from a finite element modeling of a computerized tomography of the composite. By combining the matrix viscoelastic properties and the 3D woven architecture in Abaqus, a viscoelastic homogenized model of the composite was numerically obtained in this work.

4 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES AND RESULTS

4.1 Specimens manufacturing

3D woven interlock fabric and DGEBF epoxy resin (DiGlycidyl Ether of Bisphenol F) were studied in this work as structural composites. Plates of one ply were manufactured by RTM, a ply being of four interlock layers. An unbalanced warp/weft ratio of the fabric was used. Three configurations were chosen to emphasize the material response during mechanical testing: warp tows oriented at 45° from the longitudinal plate direction, and weft and warp tows respectively oriented along the longitudinal plate direction. Each configuration was repeated three times for consistency. A rectangular RTM steel mold was used to perform longitudinal injections. Nine rectangular plates of 280x139x3.35mm were manufactured, allowing to cut four composite specimens into each plate. A fiber volume fraction of 58% was targeted.

The epoxy resin was first preheated at 100°C and degassed during 30 min. The resin was then injected into the heated mold at a constant flow rate of 20ml/min. A compaction pressure was applied right after and during the whole process to prevent porosities in the final part [20]. Two temperature steps were hold to ensure the complete polymerization of the resin. The parts were cooled down in the closed tool until the internal temperature reached 100°C. The parts were finally ejected from the tool cavity to cool down by air convection at room temperature. Specimens of 250 x 25 x 3.35 mm on each direction were cut by a waterjet cutting system based on ASTM D3039/D3039M [21]. The selected width ensured a minimum number of representative elementary volume (REV) of the interlock fabric.

4.2 Testing procedure

Creep tests were carried out on the fully cured rectangular composite specimens in tension using a universal testing machine coupled with an oven, based on ASTM D3039/D3039M [21]. A biaxial extensometer was installed on the specimens, measuring longitudinal and transversal strains. Creep tests were performed at six isothermals from 120°C to 200°C. Based on the work of Benavente et. al [22], more significant creep behavior was expected in a tolerable timeframe in this temperature interval. The force applied on specimens was selected based on monotone tension tests previously ran, thus ensuring the elastic domain of the material. Thermocouples were placed around the specimens to control

temperature variations and each isothermal was hold one hour prior to applying the load force to ensure the sample and apparatus thermal equilibrium. The measured strains by the extensometer were initializing from there not to take the specimens' thermal expansion in consideration.

4.3 Results

The results will be presented in the oral session during the conference. Creep behavior is significant from 30min to 150min after applying the load force, depending on the isothermal step. The experimental results will be compared to the predictions of the proposed temperature and cure dependent linearly viscoelastic model.

Poisson's ratio and Coefficients of Thermal Expansion (CTEs) will also be presented from the biaxial measurement of the composite specimens' strains, during the creep tests and the temperature stabilization phases before applying the load, respectively.

5 CONCLUSION

A temperature and cure dependent linearly viscoelastic homogenized model of composite with 3D woven interlock fabric was developed in this work. The proposed mathematical and geometrical modeling was compared with experimental creep responses of composite specimens made of a 3D *through the thickness/angle interlock woven* carbon fabric and epoxy resin. The temperature dependency was the main comparison on this work since only fully cured composite plates were tested. the cure dependency was confirmed on epoxy specimens in previous work.

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